

CIVIL SECURITY IN THE CONTEXT OF SOCIAL CHANGE

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the concept of civil security amid contemporary social transformations, particularly the challenges posed by mass migration, integration policies, and the evolving role of civil society. The aim is to identify conceptual gaps and practical shortcomings in current integration policies. Using a qualitative, interdisciplinary methodology that draws on sociology, political science, and security studies, the paper examines how globalisation, armed conflict, demographic shifts, and economic disparity affect public safety, integration policy, and state responsibility. It critically assesses the implementation of the European Union's Common Basic Principles for the Integration of Third-Country Nationals and evaluates the practical outcomes of these policies, using Slovakia as a case study. The analysis highlights Slovakia's limited exposure to mass migration compared to Western Europe, and contrasts the relative success in integrating Ukrainian refugees with the long-standing marginalisation of the Roma community. The study argues for a redefinition of civil security to include not only protection from external threats, but also internal stability, social cohesion, and the balance of civil rights and obligations. It concludes with recommendations for more effective, sustainable integration policies, the consistent enforcement of civic duties, and a more context-sensitive approach to managing societal change.

Keywords: security, threat, citizen, civil society, civil rights, migration

INTRODUCTION

The current period is a time of profound social change caused by global processes affecting politics, economics, law, culture and the everyday lives of citizens. Large multinational corporations are having a huge impact on the lives of citizens, influencing the politics and economy of countries and even entire continents in their efforts to gain and maintain profits. There is an undisguised struggle for raw material resources. Various tools are being used, ranging from lobbying, both legal and illegal, to collusion. The worst means of that is a military conflict. Wars are the cause and source of suffering for entire nations. As a result of wars, millions of people leave their

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homes and seek refuge in other countries. In addition to military conflicts, the cause of emigration is poverty and the desire to find a better life in another country. European countries with advanced economies and high levels of social security are popular destinations. Migrants are a diverse group of people, differing in language, culture, religious affiliation, political views, ideology and personal interests. All these factors shape the attitude of a given individual towards society. Foreigners are confronted with the legal and social system of the host environment. A major challenge is the need to integrate these arriving foreigners. Principles have been adopted to underpin a coherent European framework for the integration of third-country nationals. Despite the efforts made and the enormous financial resources spent on the integration of foreigners; the results can be considered modest. It appears that even the economically strong states of Europe have not been able to integrate such large numbers of foreigners. Negative phenomena such as increased crime, the creation of so-called NO-GO zones, where foreigners create a parallel self-government, are manifesting themselves. This is the cause of rising tensions and increasingly frequent manifestations of civil discontent. This article employs a qualitative, interdisciplinary approach to examine the concept of civil security in the context of contemporary social transformations. The analysis is grounded in a synthesis of theoretical frameworks from sociology, political science, and security studies, combined with empirical data from European Union institutions, UNHCR statistics, and national reports on migration and integration. A case study of the Slovak Republic is used to contextualize general trends and highlight specific challenges related to integration and social cohesion. The study draws on document analysis, policy review, and socio-political reflection to assess the effectiveness of integration measures, especially in light of ongoing migration pressures and the persistent marginalisation of specific social groups. The aim is to identify conceptual gaps and practical shortcomings in current integration policies, and to propose alternative strategies that are enforceable, sustainable, and adaptable to national contexts.

1 CIVIL SOCIETY

Civil society is primarily understood as a group of people having a relationship to a given state, or to an administrative unit defined by a certain territory. An example of such an administrative unit is the European Union, which is not considered to be a state in the classical sense of the term 'state', but which, on the other hand, has built up corresponding structures, such as the European Commission and the European Parliament, and whose inhabitants are citizens of the European Union.

Historically, citizenship is primarily characterised by a certain set of rights that the citizen had to win in the struggle with the state. Civil society and the state have thus been pitted against each other. It is forgotten that citizenship rights presuppose the state as their guarantor, that the modern state was not created 'against' the citizen, but precisely in accordance with his or her will as the fundamental guarantor of his or her rights. The modern state both respects and guarantees civil rights, and the state is in turn controlled by civil society. Civil society is then complemented by the rule of law; they presuppose and require each other; one cannot exist without the other. The rule of law, guaranteed by the state, is a prerequisite for the proper functioning of society and a guarantor of citizens' security (Križovský, 2011, p. 61-62). Citizenship is of fundamental importance for every citizen, as it defines his or her legal, political and social relationship to the society in which he or she lives (Macháček, 2008, pp. 77-94).

Sociological reflection on the development of this process in classical democracies, as contained in the work of the English sociologist T. H. The civic dimension in the 18th century, the political dimension in the 19th century and the social dimension in the 20th century. To understand the concept of citizenship, it is necessary to answer basic questions. The first question is what **rights** the different dimensions of citizenship entail, the second question is what the **instruments** for their realization are. Finally, we ask whether there are independent **institutions** in society that guarantee or supervise the provision of these rights.

Tab. 1: Citizenship according to T. H. Marshall

Criteria/ Aspects of cizitenship	When did it evolve?	What rights does it include?	Instruments of implementation	Responsible institutions
CIVIL	18 th century	personal liberty, private property, protection from the state, contractual relations, freedom of speech and religion	rule of law (legal state)	courts
POLITICAL	19 th century	articipation in the exercise of political power (as a voter or member of a representative body)	election process, universal suffrage	parliament, local authority
SOCIAL	20 th century	economic and social security according to the prevailing standard in society	housing, education, health care, social security, unemployment benefits, pensions	Social Insurance, Social Security

Source: Wallace, 1993, pp. 163-176.

In the context of the functioning of the European Union, civil society has acquired a transnational dimension. One of the four strategic priorities of the European Commission is to promote new forms of European governance. Governance is defined as the rules, mechanisms and practices that influence the decision-making process and allow for the maximum involvement of European citizens in this process. The modernisation of the functioning of the European public rests on five basic principles: openness, participation, accountability, efficiency and coherence.

Tab. 2: Principles of civil modernisation in Europe.

<i>Openness</i>	ensures information and active communication with young people in their own language so that they understand Europe's actions and policies that affect them.
<i>Participation</i>	ensures that young people are consulted and involved in decisions that affect them individually and the life of their community in general.
<i>Accountability</i>	the development of a new and newly structured form of cooperation between the Member States and the European institutions is also in the interests of finding ways of generating an appropriate level of accountability and respect for young people's aspirations.
<i>Effectiveness</i>	ensuring that what young people have to offer can be a response to society's challenges, so that young people can contribute to the success of the various sectoral policies that concern them and contribute to building the Europe of the future.
<i>Coherence</i>	to develop awareness of the existence of different policy approaches concerning young people and to enable them to intervene at different levels where this is useful.

Source: Nový impulz pre... Available at:
<https://www.litcentrum.sk/dielo/novy-impulz-pre-europsku-mladez-biela-kniha-europskej-komisie>>.

A modern civil society is built based on respect for and realisation of the political, social, cultural and economic rights of citizens. From this perspective, we can speak of the following dimensions of modern citizenship:

Political/legal dimension

Political citizenship refers to political rights and responsibilities in relation to the political system. Political rights, enshrined in the Constitution, include freedom of expression and the right to information, the right to petition, the right to assemble peacefully, the right to associate freely, the right to participate in the conduct of public affairs directly or by

freely choosing one's representatives, the right to freely compete in political forces, including the right to dissent.

Responsibility in the exercise of political rights lies in the requirement to comply with the obligations and restrictions laid down by law. Many 'activists', in exercising political rights, are primarily guided by the principle 'what is not prohibited by law is permitted'. In doing so, they forget the moral dimension of their actions. It is true that indiscriminate political 'activism', carried out on the edge of the law, may have a short-term effect, but in the long term it is counterproductive. It brings discord, nervousness and even hostility into civil society. It can lead to disturbances of public order and, in extreme cases, to criminal activity. Recently, several politically motivated violent crimes have been committed not only abroad, but also in Slovakia. The assassination attempt of the Prime Minister of the Slovak Republic is the most extreme case.

Social dimension

Social citizenship refers to the relations between individuals in society, it is associated with demands of loyalty, solidarity but also responsibility for one's social status. Social rights include the right to fair and satisfactory working conditions, the right to associate freely with others to protect one's social interests, the right to strike, the right to increased occupational health protection and special working conditions for women, adolescents and the disabled, the right to adequate material security in old age and in the event of incapacity for work as well as in the event of the loss of a breadwinner, and the right to health protection. Citizens' social rights are implemented mainly through the social security system. The level of social security depends on the amount of money injected into the system, which operates on the principle of solidarity. The ideal state is when inputs and outputs are in balance. Recent developments point to an imbalanced situation that requires subsidising the social security system. There are several causes that are straining the social security system, including low birth rates, an ageing population, which is associated with a steadily rising retirement age, the number of economically active individuals, but also, for example, the performance of the economy.

Loyalty and responsibility mean recognising that if I want to enjoy the benefits of the social system, I must contribute my share to it. The state does not have sufficient mechanisms in place to eliminate behaviour, when selected groups are only benefiting from the social system and not adding their fair share to it. The reason for this is the imperfection of legislation, the unwillingness of the competent authorities to deal with "unpleasant matters" and the influence of interest organisations. The consequence is the dissatisfaction of citizens and an attempt to use or abuse the problem in the political battle of political parties.

The cultural dimension

Cultural citizenship refers to the awareness of a shared cultural heritage. Cultural rights include the right to education, freedom of scientific research and the arts, and the right of access to cultural wealth. Closely linked to the right of access to cultural wealth is the duty to protect and develop it. As a rule, cultural wealth is linked to a nation, a nationality, which originated and developed in a certain territory. We are talking about both tangible and intangible wealth. This includes language, customs, traditions, artistic expressions, architecture and the nature of interpersonal relations.

The protection of cultural wealth is of particular importance in the current period of turbulent globalisation processes and mass migration. Migrants bring with them their culture, which is deeply rooted in them, and, as the countries affected by mass migration show, often they are unable to integrate into the new society, creating cultural communities on the territory of the host country. So-called NO-GO zones are emerging where the relevant state authorities, including the police, have difficulty exercising their powers.

The issue of the protection and development of the national language, while respecting the rights of national minorities, also deserves attention. The media play a major role in this. In an attempt to attract the attention of young people in particular, but also because of convenience, laziness in taking over the news and often a lack of language training, presenters resort to using foreign language expressions at the expense of the Slovak language.

The economic dimension

Economic citizenship refers to the relationship of the individual to the labour market and the consumer market. It includes the right to freely choose a profession and to prepare for it, the right to engage in business and other gainful activity, and the right to freely associate with others to protect one's economic interests. The saying goes that money makes the world go round. This is doubly true in the area of the labour market and consumption. The structure of production is changing; in many countries, manufacturing industries such as metallurgy and mining have disappeared, but some crafts are also disappearing; many crafts have been transferred from the sphere of production to the sphere of art, e.g. blacksmithing, tinkering, knitting. There has been a massive development of electronics and computer science. The labour market and the training of the workforce must also adapt to this trend. Many people are unable to find a place on the labour market because they are not interested in their current profession and, on the other hand, they do not meet the qualification requirements of the newly emerging industries. The state has taken certain measures to address this problem, offering retraining courses, but also, for example, the possibility of early retirement. There is an effort to attract skilled labour from abroad. Here again we are faced with the issue of migration. Slovakia is struggling with the problem of skilled labour emigrating abroad, where young people in particular expect better financial rewards. There are justified demands for opening up the labour market to third-country residents, and the question of their integration is an important one.

2 MIGRATION AND INTEGRATION OF FOREIGNERS

Civil society, with the respective dimensions we have explained, forms the foundation for integration projects such as the European Union. At the same time, it could be argued that the assimilation of migrants into civil society structures is not only welcome but also crucial for addressing the security challenges associated with migration and foreign elements.

At the end of 2023, an estimated 117.3 million people worldwide were forcibly displaced as a result of persecution, conflict, violence, human rights violations and events seriously disrupting public order. Based on

operational data, UNHCR estimates that forced displacement continued to increase in the first four months of 2024 and is likely to exceed 120 million by the end of April 2024.

The global refugee population increased by 7 per cent during the year to reach 43.4 million . This includes 31.6 million refugees and people in refugee-like situations and 5.8 million additional people in need of international protection under UNHCR's mandate, as well as 6 million Palestinian refugees under UNRWA's mandate. Compared to a decade ago, the total number of refugees worldwide has more than tripled.

Nearly two-thirds of all refugees under UNHCR's mandate and others in need of international protection come from just four countries.

Syria	6,3 mil.
Venezuela	6,2 mil.
Ukraine	6,1 mil.
Afghanistan	6,1 mil.

Colombia, Germany, the Islamic Republic of Iran, Turkey and Uganda have sheltered nearly a third of the world's refugees and other people in need of international protection.

Iran	3,8 mil.
Turkey	3,1 mil.
Columbia	2,8 mil.
Germany	2,7 mil.
Uganda	1,7 mil.

The majority of refugees remain close to their country of origin, with 69 per cent hosted in neighbouring countries at the end of 2023. Low- and middle-income countries continue to host the majority of the world's refugees, with 75 per cent of refugees living in low- and middle-income countries (*Global Trends, 2024*).

The European Union institutions have been dealing with integration issues for a long time. The first edition of the Handbook on Integration for

policy-makers and practitioners was published in November 2004. The Hague Programme adopted by the European Council of 4-5 November 2004 underlines the need for better coordination of national integration policies and EU initiatives in this field. The Agenda further states that a framework based on common principles, supported by clear objectives and means of evaluation, should be the basis for future initiatives in the EU (*The Hague Programme...*, 2005). On 19 November 2004, the Justice and Home Affairs Council adopted a set of common basic principles to form a coherent European framework for the integration of third-country nationals. These principles emphasize that integration is a **dynamic, two-way process**, involving mutual adaptation by both immigrants and residents of EU Member States. At its core, integration requires **respect for the fundamental values of the European Union**. **Employment** plays a central role in this process, serving not only as a means for immigrants to contribute to and engage with their host societies but also as a way to make this participation visible. Equally crucial is the acquisition of **basic knowledge about the language, history, and institutions** of the host country, which is considered a prerequisite for successful integration. Education emerges as a key tool in preparing immigrants—and especially their descendants—to become active, successful members of society. Furthermore, equal and **non-discriminatory access to public and private goods, services, and institutions** is essential for fostering true integration. Regular and meaningful interaction between immigrants and native citizens is another pillar of the integration framework. This includes **intercultural dialogue, joint community initiatives, and improved urban living conditions**, all of which help build mutual understanding and social cohesion. The **freedom to practice different cultures and religions**, as guaranteed by the Charter of Fundamental Rights, is to be protected—provided these practices do not infringe upon European fundamental rights or national laws. Immigrant **participation in democratic processes**, particularly at the local level, is strongly encouraged as a way of shaping integration policies and promoting social inclusion. An effective integration strategy must be embedded across **all policy areas and levels of government**, ensuring consistency and coordination. Setting **clear**

objectives, indicators, and evaluation mechanisms is critical for assessing progress and refining policies. Integration measures must be proactive and inclusive, developed with the involvement of **regional authorities, social partners, and immigrant organizations**. The process of integration is underpinned by several foundational pillars:

1. Language proficiency in the host country's language,
2. Access to employment,
3. Secure housing,
4. Access to education,
5. Elimination of all forms of discrimination,
6. Ongoing monitoring and analysis,
7. Promotion of a culture of coexistence,
8. Civic participation in public life, and
9. Adaptation of public services to reflect changing demographic realities.

These elements together form the backbone of an inclusive and sustainable integration policy within the European Union.

Have the Common Basic Principles for the Integration of Third-Country Nationals been applied in real policy in the countries of the European Union? What is the outcome of the integration efforts of the European Union authorities? It must be stated that integration efforts have failed because of the enormous increase in illegal migration, where migrants have flowed and continue to flow into Europe in numbers of millions per year. Mass immigration has become a problem for those countries that have allowed the uncontrolled entry of migrants into their territory. Recently, we have seen efforts to redistribute migrants among all the countries of the European Union, and also attempts to deport foreigners back to their home countries. Many countries in the Schengen area have introduced border controls in an attempt to restrict the entry of migrants into their territory.

The following figure shows the number and trend of illegal crossings of the EU borders in 2024 (Zmušková, 2025).

Fig. 1: Number of irregular border-crossings Jan-Dec 2024

According to Eurostat data for 2023, the percentage of third-country nationals by country of residence in the European Union is as follows: Germany - 28%, France - 16%, Spain - 16%, Italy - 14%, the other 23 EU countries - 27%. (European Court of Auditors, 2025)

The Slovak Republic is one of the countries that has not been affected by mass migration. Slovakia has not been and is not a destination for migrants and, moreover, it is among the countries that have taken measures against illegal migration. An exception is made for citizens of Ukraine, who found refuge in Slovakia even before the war. Moreover, the vast majority of Ukrainians have no problem integrating into Slovak society. As of June 30, 2020, Slovakia was home to 145,940 foreigners, representing

approximately 2.67% of the total population of 5,457,926. Of this number, 88,245 individuals (1.62%) were nationals of third countries—those outside the European Union—while 57,695 individuals (1.05%) were citizens of EU member states residing in Slovakia.

Among third-country nationals, the most represented group came from Ukraine, with 39,578 individuals, making up nearly 45% of this demographic. Serbia followed with 16,659 individuals (18.88%), and Vietnam was third with 6,413 people (7.3%). Other significant countries of origin included Russia (5,317; 6%), China (2,707; 3.1%), North Macedonia (1,683; 1.91%), South Korea (1,515; 1.72%), Iran (1,288; 1.46%), India (1,042; 1.2%), and the United States (1,049; 1.2%).

These figures highlight that while the proportion of foreigners in Slovakia remains relatively low compared to Western European countries, the country has a diverse foreign population primarily composed of individuals from Eastern Europe and Asia. The high representation of neighboring and culturally proximate nations, such as Ukraine and Serbia, suggests regional migration dynamics, whereas the presence of communities from Vietnam, China, and South Korea reflects long-term settlement trends and economic or educational migration.

Given these patterns, integration policies should prioritize language acquisition, access to education and employment, and non-discriminatory access to services, while also supporting civic participation and cultural dialogue. This approach is crucial to ensuring the successful inclusion of these communities within Slovak society. (hrl.sk, 2025)

While much of the current European discourse on integration focuses on the influx of third-country nationals and the challenges of cross-cultural adaptation, similar difficulties have long been present within national borders. The case of Slovakia illustrates that integration is not solely a matter of accommodating newcomers from abroad, but also of addressing the persistent exclusion of historically marginalised groups. One such group is the Roma community, whose integration poses a deeply rooted societal challenge despite centuries of coexistence. The following section turns to this domestic dimension of integration, comparing it to the broader

European context and examining why previous efforts have struggled to bring lasting results.

Problems with integration into mainstream society do not only affect foreigners. We are referring to the integration of people in the marginalised Roma community. We are not referring to the Roma community as a whole, but to a part of the Roma community that is struggling to get out of poverty. We see the problem in the approach that has been taken so far to solving the so-called Roma problem. We are of the opinion that the solution lies in equal access to all inhabitants, regardless of whether they are Roma or non-Roma.

There have been attempts to integrate the Roma into society since the reign of Maria Theresa. Integration measures have always been in keeping with the times and have always suited the existing government authorities more than the Roma themselves. One cannot be surprised at their far-sighted attitude today.

It is clear to all of us that the majority society will never, and cannot, accept and accept the way of life currently led by the marginalised part of the Roma community. Within the framework of the fight against poverty, various programmes have been adopted and implemented, such as local comprehensive development strategies aimed at helping municipalities with at least 15% of the Roma population.

The main problem is that, in the past and even today, huge sums of money have been spent on social benefits, but these are used inefficiently. In the days of social benefits there is great abundance, in a few days there is hunger again. This situation is exploited by usurers living in the community, almost the entire amount of social benefits ending up in their pockets. They then lend the Roma their own money in return for high 'interest'. Would it not be more sensible to pay social benefits not once a month, but once a week? If the usurers know how to do it, so could the state.

A major problem is the question of housing. Members of marginalised Roma communities are unwilling to pay for electricity, water, or gas and firewood. In addition, the houses in which they live are so devastated that they are not suitable for living in after a short period of time. If the number of family members increases, shacks are added to the house, which grow

day by day. The problem is solved by building new houses, albeit of a low standard, where these Roma are moved in. However, in a very short period of time, within five years or so, these houses are 'bulldozed'. This means that they are so dilapidated that they are unfit for habitation. There are plenty of examples from the past and the present, even in our own neighbourhood, in Košice. An example is the Lunik IX housing estate in Košice, where a prefabricated block of flats had to be demolished due to its statics being disturbed. Huge damage has been caused, but no one is being held to account.

There is a lot of money being poured through the implementation of projects. The flaw in all the projects is that they are short-term, that the money is intended to create suitable conditions for improving the quality of life of the Roma, but not for maintaining the quality of life. In fact, we are always moving in a certain circle in this way. There is a need to change the philosophy of the approach to solving the so-called Roma problem. From the point of view of solving social problems, we need to stop looking at the Roma as an ethnic group. Every inhabitant, every citizen of the state, is a bearer of rights and obligations. It is necessary to treat everyone equally, to consistently demand the fulfilment of obligations, and to apply the rights of each individual. It is in the demanding of duties that our society is inconsistent. It is more convenient to make some declarations, allocate a bundle of money, and after some time state that there has been some progress, even though there has been none, than to solve problems by implementing even unpopular measures, without which the situation cannot change.

It has not been possible to integrate the Roma population fully in the 700-plus years since their arrival in Europe. This applies not only to Slovakia, but to all the countries in which the Roma population is settled. In some countries (France, Italy), the Roma still live a nomadic way of life. Is Europe capable of integrating millions of migrants from Asia and Africa? If something is to change in a relatively short period of time, i.e. in the lifetime of a generation, some measures should be taken, for example:

- 1.) Pay welfare benefits on a weekly basis - even if the money for this comes from welfare payments.

2.) When designing projects to improve the lives of the Roma, allocate funds to maintain what is built, to maintain the quality of life.

3.) Employ Roma from marginalised communities, even at the cost of artificial employment - do not just give them money, they need to acquire work habits.

4.) Gradually integrate them into society through selection - build new housing estates with complete facilities, including job opportunities, where to provide housing for those members of the marginalised community who want to work, to be educated. If they don't get educated, they won't work, they will go back to their original environment. It is not possible for those who do not want to integrate to be paid for by others.

5.) To build boarding schools where children of maladjusted parents will be placed, thus modifying the regime of contact with the children so that they can negatively influence the educational process as little as possible.

6.) Apply the principle of merit in the payment of social benefits.

Security, secure environment

Safety is a highly valued value of every human being. Since the beginning of man's existence, he has constantly assessed his security. At the same time, the subjective view of security must be emphasised. Each person perceives and evaluates his personal security on the basis of experience, knowledge and, in the vast and complex conditions of contemporary civilisation, especially on the basis of information. What is most important for each individual is his or her own security. We can say that it is a matter of security prestige. We are dealing with the rapid development of civilisation, which creates the conditions for increasing and multifaceted dangers.

Diagram 1: Structure of the most important factors to be taken into account to define the concept of security

The security interests defined in the Security Concept of the Slovak Republic are based on the needs of the citizens and the state. The vital interests of the Slovak Republic are based on basic long-term needs and are of decisive importance for guaranteeing the life and security of citizens, the existence and functioning of the State. These interests are primarily the following:

- guaranteeing the security of the Slovak Republic, its sovereignty and integrity,
- preserving and developing the democratic foundations of the state, its internal security and order, protecting the life and health of citizens,
- ensuring sustainable economic, social, environmental and cultural development of society, together with the protection of the state's important infrastructures and the environment,
- preserving peace and stability in Central Europe, associated with the expansion of the zone of democracy, security and prosperity,
- the important interests of the Slovak Republic create broader prerequisites for the realisation of the vital interests of the Slovak Republic by influencing both the international (external) and the internal conditions. Important interests of the Slovak Republic are primarily:
 - o maintenance of peace and stability in the world and prevention of tensions and crises, or their timely and effective resolution by peaceful means,
 - o good relations with immediate neighbours and development of all forms of mutually beneficial regional cooperation,
 - o internal political stability based on a corresponding society-wide consensus on issues of vital and important interests of the Slovak Republic,
 - o achievement of a dynamic transition of the economy of the Slovak Republic to a more ecologically balanced one, more efficient and resource-diversified market economy capable of adequately meeting the needs of citizens,
 - o guaranteeing social peace and stability in society based on respect for equal rights of all inhabitants without distinction of political affiliation, religion, gender, race, belonging to different national or social groups,
 - o achieving environmental security within internal and international structures.

Important interests of the Slovak Republic create broader prerequisites for the realisation of the vital interests of the Slovak Republic by influencing both international (external) and internal conditions. Important interests of the Slovak Republic are in particular:

- maintenance of peace and stability in the world and prevention of tensions and crises, or their timely and effective resolution by peaceful means,
- good relations with immediate neighbours and development of all forms of mutually beneficial regional cooperation,
- internal political stability based on a corresponding society-wide consensus on issues of vital and important interests of the Slovak Republic,
- achievement of a dynamic transition of the economy of the Slovak Republic to a more ecologically balanced one, more efficient and resource-diversified market economy capable of adequately meeting the needs of citizens,
- guaranteeing social peace and stability in society based on respect for equal rights of all inhabitants without distinction of political affiliation, religion, gender, race, belonging to different national or social groups,
- achieving environmental security within internal and international structures.

3 SECURITY ENVIRONMENT

The security environment is a part of the natural, social and cultural environment in which the conditions of existence and development of social objects, their activities, relationships and interests are primarily determined by security. It expresses, in particular, the spatial dimension of security associated with the action of subjects in a particular time and under certain conditions. It is the broadest concept that expresses the security situation in a certain space at a certain time, this security situation being the result of the activities of the relevant security actors (security authorities, institutions, states, coalitions of states, etc.). The security environment is not an empty space, but a certain quality that not only limits the possibilities

of social development, but by its critical state reflects and signals the critical state of society itself. The security environment is characterised through the demarcation of a certain geographical territory, which is usually also determined by other socio-economic, demographic and cultural-historical factors. Other factors that define the security space are the security actors located and operating within it, the existence of security risks and threats, the sustainability of development, as well as environmental ethics and an ecologically friendly value orientation (Mesároš, 2009).

The subject of the analysis of the environment in relation to citizen safety may be information on:

1. Information on the urban characteristics of the environment, which will include an assessment of the size of the settlement in which the facility is located, the type of development, the characteristics of the surroundings of the facility that may have an impact on the safety of the residents,
2. Information on social criminogenic factors, which may be considered as the state of the standard of living of the population, the level of employment, the proportion of socially deprived citizens, etc.
3. Information on quantitative and qualitative indicators of crime in and around the environment under consideration. In doing so, it is useful to assess:
 - the type of crime, which is characterised in particular by the aspect in question (types of crime and their form),
 - the demographic aspect, which consists in the application of aspects such as gender, age, social or economic status of the perpetrator, etc,
 - the territorial aspect, which makes it possible to examine the spatial distribution of crime by region; since the absolute values of crime are largely determined by the size of the population, in order to objectify the share of regions in total crime, it is more convenient to monitor and analyse relative data, which more accurately characterise the riskiness of the

- spatial units under study (e.g. districts, towns, neighbourhoods, etc.),
- the urban aspect, which makes it possible to analyse the share of the inhabitants of urban areas (cities, municipalities) in total crime and in its individual types; applying this aspect of crime assessment shows that cities are more risky in terms of crime than smaller rural settlements, which is also due to the fact that in cities there is greater anonymity, a higher concentration of people resulting from greater employment opportunities, and greater concentration of material values and larger enterprises in cities; crime in larger cities is also increased by migrants from the countryside who commute for work or to commit crime, or by foreigners (legal or illegal migrants), members of organised crime groups, etc. ,
 - crime trends, with a particular focus on property crime trends.
4. Information on the situation in the field of protection of property and objects, in particular the deployment of police and security bodies, the possibilities of using intervention units in the protection of objects, in particular with regard to the time of intervention, etc.
 5. Information on the state of citizens' opinions and moods, their attitude towards crime, the state of legal awareness, opinions on the state and provision of their security, the degree of tolerance of citizens towards property crime, etc.
 6. Information on the natural conditions in the environment, the frequency, extent and severity of natural disasters that could threaten the protected object.
 7. Information on the stable and mobile sources of industrial accidents in the environment that could affect security.

The result of this analysis is the definition of the assumptions of risks of a social, technical and environmental nature that may endanger the protected interest - life or property of citizens and legal persons.

An important factor influencing contemporary security is both the globalisation process and international integration processes. The removal of administrative and political barriers between states has not only enabled the free movement of people, money and goods, but also improved conditions for the activities and operations of organised crime. Criminal elements can now operate on a truly transnational scale without serious obstacles. Even natural disasters, industrial accidents or the spread of contagious diseases do not respect national borders. The impact of globalisation means that no country is isolated from negative phenomena whose sources can be found even in geographically distant areas.

CONCLUSION

This paper examines the evolving concept of civic security in the context of contemporary social change, with particular emphasis on migration, integration, and the role of civil society. Drawing on European Union policy frameworks, empirical migration data, and the sociological theory of citizenship, the study explores how global processes—such as armed conflict, economic inequality, and cultural displacement—affect public safety, social cohesion, and state responsibility. The paper critically assesses the effectiveness of the EU’s Common Basic Principles for the Integration of Third-Country Nationals and highlights the limitations of integration efforts, particularly in countries experiencing large-scale or culturally disparate migration. A special focus is placed on Slovakia as a case study, contrasting successful integration of Ukrainian refugees with the long-standing marginalisation of the Roma community. The paper argues that civic security must be redefined to encompass not only protection from external threats but also the internal stability of democratic societies, which depends on the balanced exercise of rights and responsibilities. Through a qualitative and interdisciplinary methodology, the research identifies policy gaps and proposes a more coherent, enforceable, and context-sensitive approach to integration and social policy. Currently, the threats arising from military conflicts, both in Ukraine and in the Middle East, are at the forefront of concern. There are also risks from unstable political regimes, unstable and insecure borders allowing illegal migration and smuggling (of weapons,

drugs, goods, etc.), ethnic and religious conflicts, scarcity of natural resources and, of course, organised crime, terrorism and criminality. Today, security is also taking on a social dimension and requires tackling problems such as unemployment, poverty in third countries, mass migration and overcrowding in certain agglomerations. Internationally, we are witnessing a power struggle between the world's great powers, the US, Russia and China, for influence over their spheres of interest. There is a drive for control of raw material resources. There is protectionism in trade and economic competition. Economic development is threatened by sanctions and tariff barriers. There is open talk of a change in the world order, but we do not yet know exactly what this change will look like and what it will mean. In the context of these social changes, civil society is facing new challenges which it will have to cope with.

RESOURCES

- Aktuálne štatistiky o pobyte cudzincov žijúcich na Slovensku.* [online] Available at: <<https://www.hrl.sk/sk/o-nas/aktuality/aktualne-statistiky-o-pobyte-cudzincov-zijucich-na-slovensku>> [Accessed 27/5/2025].
- Križovský, S. (2009). *Migrácia, chudoba, nezamestnanosť – bezpečnostné aspekty.* In: *Zborník príspevkov z vedeckej konferencie s medzinárodnou účasťou Migrácia, chudoba, nezamestnanosť.* Košice: UPJŠ, ISBN 978-80-970306-0-5.
- Križovský, S. (2011). *Základné kategórie občianskej bezpečnosti.* In: *Karlovsrská právnická revue – Vysoká škola Karlovy Vary*, Vol. 7(1), pp. 61-62, ISSN 180-2193.
- Macháček, L. (2008). *Občianstvo a občianska spoločnosť: Didaktické dimenzie.* In: *Slovenská politologická revue*, Vol. 8(3), pp. 77-94.
- Mesároš, M. (2009). *Riadenie bezpečnostných systémov.* Košice: Multiprint, ISBN 978-80-89282-37-1.
- Rejtšpís, J., et. al. (2004). *Manažérstvo bezpečnostných rizík.* Žilina: Žilinská univerzita, pp. 119-122.

- The Hague Programme: strengthening freedom, security and justice in the European Union.* [online] Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=oj:JOC_2005_053_R_0001_01> [Accessed 27/5/2025].
- Wallace, C. (1993). *Koncepcia občianstva v súčasnej svetovej sociológii.* In: Sociológia, Vol. 25(3), p. 163.
- Zmušková, B. (2025). *Nelegálna migrácia do EÚ klesla o tretinu, pomohol boj proti prevádzacom.* [online] Available at: <<https://euractiv.sk/section/spolocnost/news/nelegalna-migracia-do-eu-klesla-o-tretinu-pomohol-boj-proti-prevadzacom/>> [Accessed 27/5/2025].
- Nový impulz pre európsku mládež. Biela kniha Európskej komisie.* [online] Available at: <<https://www.litcentrum.sk/dielo/novy-impulz-pre-europsku-mladez-biela-kniha-europskej-komisie>> [Accessed 27/5/2025].
- Global Trends (UNHCR).* [online] Available at: <<https://www.unhcr.org/global-trends>>.
- Report.* In: *European Court of Auditors.* [online] Available at: <<http://eca.europa.eu/sk/publications/sr2024-26>> [Accessed 27/5/2025].